

ON INCOMPRESSIBLE MULTIDIMENSIONAL NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT. This work presents a theoretical investigation of incompressible multidimensional networks defined by a generalized graph representation. In particular, we study the incompressibility (i.e., algorithmic randomness) of snapshot-dynamic networks and multiplex networks in comparison to the incompressibility of more general forms of multidimensional networks, from which snapshot-dynamic networks or multiplex networks are particular cases. In addition, we study some of their network topological properties and discuss how these may be related to real-world complex networks. First, we show that incompressible snapshot-dynamic (or multiplex) networks carry an amount of algorithmic information that is linearly dominated by the size of the set of time instants (or layers). This contrasts with the algorithmic information carried by an incompressible general dynamic (or multilayer) network that is of the quadratic order of the size of the set of time instants (or layers). Furthermore, incompressible general multidimensional networks inherit most of the topological properties from their respective isomorphic graph. Hence, we show that these networks have very short diameter, high k -connectivity, and degrees of the order of half of the network size within a strong-asymptotically dominated standard deviation. Particularly, we show that incompressible general multidimensional networks have transtemporal (or crosslayer) edges. Thus, this property may not correspond to the underlying structure of many real-world networks that can be properly modeled by snapshot-like multidimensional networks.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In a general sense, a multidimensional network (also known as high-order network) is any network that has additional representational structures. For example, this is the case of dynamic (i.e., time-varying) networks [11, 21, 24, 27], multilayer networks [5, 15, 18], and dynamic multilayer networks [29, 30]. As the interest and pervasiveness of complex network modelling and network analysis increase in network science or in complex systems science, proper representations of such networks into new extensions of graph-theoretical abstractions has become an important topic of investigation [18, 19, 22].

In this regard, the general scope of this paper is to study the plain and prefix algorithmic randomness of multidimensional networks. Within the theoretical framework of algorithmic information theory, complex networks theory, and graph theory, we study incompressibility (i.e., algorithmic randomness) and computably irreducible information content (i.e., plain or prefix algorithmic complexity) in generalized graph representations.

As shown in [16, 23, 35], approaches to network complexity based on classical (or statistical) information theory have presented useful tools to find, estimate or measure underlying graph-theoretic topological structures or properties. However, it has been shown that these estimations or resulting values are not invariant to language description [35]. This comes from the reliance on probability distributions that require making a choice of feature of interest relevant to the measure of interest. For example, the node degrees for the study of their distribution in a network disregards other representations of the same object (network) and its possible underlying generating mechanism. While some of these statistical approaches may be useful when a feature of interest is selected they can only capture the complexity of the representation and not the object. This is in contrast to universal measures of randomness such as algorithmic complexity whose invariance theorem guarantees that different representation will have convergent values. Of course, the complication is how to achieve the estimation of those universal measures which by virtue of being universal are also semi-computable and their application require, therefore, a much higher degree of methodological care compared to those measures that are simply computable such as those based on traditional statistical approaches such as entropy, or graph-theoretic such as node degree. Nevertheless, only algorithmic information theory has been giving us computably universal tools for studying incompressibility of fixed individual graphs that are not generated or defined by stochastic processes [35]. Thus, such an approach also differs from the traditional methods in random graphs theory, such as the probabilistic method.

Our approach is grounded in the theory and methods of algorithmic complexity and algorithmic randomness [7, 9, 17, 20]. In this article, we apply the results on labeling and algorithmic randomness introduced in [1], which extends the ones for classical graphs to multiaspect graphs (MAGs) [30, 31]. MAGs are formal representations of dyadic (or 2-place) relations between two arbitrary n -ary tuples and have shown fruitful representational properties to network modelling [2, 3, 30, 34] and analysis of multidimensional networks [11, 29, 32, 33]. First, we compare the algorithmic complexity and incompressibility of snapshot-dynamic networks and multiplex networks with more general forms of dynamic networks and multilayer networks, respectively. In turn, dynamic networks and multilayer networks are considered as distinct types of multidimensional (or high-order) networks. Secondly,

we present some multidimensional topological properties of incompressible general multidimensional networks. To tackle these problems in the present paper, we apply a theoretical approach by putting forward definitions, lemmas, theorems, and corollaries. Then, we discuss relations between the results.

In Sections 2 and 3, we present some background results upon which we build the contributions of this paper. In Section 4, we investigate the algorithmic randomness of snapshot-dynamic networks and multiplex networks through the calculation of the worst-case lossless compression of the characteristic string of the network. This way, one can compare these two kinds of networks with the incompressibility of more general forms of dynamic networks and multilayer networks, respectively.

Further, in Section 5, we investigate some multidimensional network topological properties of incompressible multidimensional networks. Such topological properties include, more specifically, degree distribution of composite vertices, composite diameter, and composite k -connectivity. As shown in [1], if the randomness deficiency is asymptotically bounded above by a logarithmic term of the network size, these findings follow from the fact that incompressible multidimensional networks inherit the topological properties from their respective isomorphic graphs [30]. Hence, we also derive the presence of a new multidimensional network topological property that may not correspond to underlying structures of real-world networks, e.g., of snapshot-dynamic networks or multiplex networks. In particular, we show the presence of transtemporal or crosslayer edges (i.e., edges linking vertices at non-sequential time instants or layers).

2. PRELIMINARY DEFINITIONS AND NOTATION

2.1. Multiaspect graphs. In order to represent high-order networks, we are basing our work on a generalized graph representation of dyadic relations between n -tuples [30, 31]:

Definition 2.1. Let $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{E})$ be a multiaspect graph (MAG), where \mathcal{E} is the set of existing composite edges of the MAG and \mathcal{A} is a class of sets, each of which is an *aspect*. Each aspect $\sigma \in \mathcal{A}$ is a finite set and the number of aspects $p = |\mathcal{A}|$ is called the *order* of \mathcal{G} . By an immediate convention, we call a MAG with only one aspect as a *first order* MAG, a MAG with two aspects as a *second order* MAG and so on. Each composite edge (or arrow) $e \in \mathcal{E}$ may be denoted by an ordered $2p$ -tuple $(a_1, \dots, a_p, b_1, \dots, b_p)$, where a_i, b_i are elements of the i -th aspect with $1 \leq i \leq p = |\mathcal{A}|$.

Note that $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})$ denotes the class of aspects of \mathcal{G} and $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$ denotes the *composite edge set* of \mathcal{G} . We denote the i -th aspect of \mathcal{G} as $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[i]$. So, $|\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[i]|$ denotes the number of elements in $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[i]$. In order to match the classical graph case, we adopt the convention of calling the elements of the first aspect of a MAG as *vertices*. Therefore, we also denote the set $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[1]$ of elements of the first aspect of a MAG \mathcal{G} as $V(\mathcal{G})$. Thus, a vertex should not be confused with a composite vertex. The set of all *composite vertices* \mathbf{v} of \mathcal{G} is defined by

$$\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}) = \prod_{i=1}^p \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[i]$$

and the set of all *composite edges* e of \mathcal{G} is defined by

$$\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G}) = \bigtimes_{n=1}^{2p} \mathcal{A}(G)[(n-1) \pmod{p} + 1],$$

so that, for every ordered pair (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) with $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G})$, we have $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = e \in \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G})$. Also, for every $e \in \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G})$ we have $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = e$ such that $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G})$. Thus,

$$\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}) \subseteq \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G})$$

Definition 2.2. We say a *directed* MAG (or graph) without *self-loops* is a *traditional* directed MAG (or graph), denoted as $\mathcal{G}_d = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{E})$.

Definition 2.3. We say an *undirected* MAG (or graph) without *self-loops* is a *simple* MAG (or graph), denoted as $\mathcal{G}_c = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{E})$, so that the set of all composite edges \mathbb{E} is subjected to a restriction in the form

$$\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \subseteq \mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c) := \{(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) \mid \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)\},$$

where¹ there is $Y \subseteq \mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ such that

$$\{(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \iff (\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) \in Y \wedge (\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u}) \in Y \wedge \mathbf{u} \neq \mathbf{v}$$

We will have directly from this Definition 2.3 that

$$|\mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c)| = \frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|^2 - |\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{2}$$

Concerning the presence or absence of composite edges in $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$, we defined the characteristic string [1] of a simple MAG:

Definition 2.4. Let $(e_1, \dots, e_{|\mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c)|})$ be any arbitrarily fixed ordering of composite edges of a simple MAG \mathcal{G}_c . We say that a string $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$ with $l(x) = |\mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c)|$ is a *characteristic string* of a simple MAG \mathcal{G}_c iff, for every $e_j \in \mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c)$,

$$e_j \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \iff \text{the } j\text{-th digit in } x \text{ is } 1,$$

where $1 \leq j \leq l(x)$.

We define the *composite diameter* of \mathcal{G} in an analogous way to diameter in classical graphs:

Definition 2.5. The composite diameter $D_{\mathcal{E}}(\mathcal{G})$ is the maximum value in the set of the minimum number of steps (through composite edges) in $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$ necessary to reach a composite vertex \mathbf{v} from a composite vertex \mathbf{u} , for any $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G})$.

See also [30] for paths and distances in MAGs. Moreover, as in [30]:

Definition 2.6. We say a traditional MAG \mathcal{G}_d is *isomorphic* to a traditional directed graph G when there is a bijective function $f : \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_d) \rightarrow V(G)$ such that an edge $e \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_d)$ if, and only if, the edge $(f(\pi_o(e)), f(\pi_d(e))) \in E(G)$, where π_o is a function that returns the origin vertex of an edge and the function π_d is a function that returns the destination vertex of an edge.

Thus, the reader may notice that the aspects in \mathcal{A} determine how the set \mathcal{E} will be defined and, therefore, they determine the type of network that the MAG is univocally representing: for example, a time-varying graph (TVG) as in [11, 34] or a multilayer graph as in [29]. In the particular case of dynamic networks, as defined in [11, 34], we have that:

¹That is, the adjacency matrix of this graph is symmetric.

Definition 2.7. Let $G_t = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ be a second order MAG representing a *time-varying graph* (TVG), where V is the set of vertices, T is the set of time instants, and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq V \times T \times V \times T$ is the set of (composite) edges. We denote the set of time instants of the graph $G_t = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ by $T(G_t) = \{t_0, t_1, \dots, t_{|T(G_t)|-1}\}$. Also, let $V(G_t)$ denote the set of vertices of G_t and $|V(G_t)|$ denote the cardinality of the set of vertices in G_t .

The terms *vertex* and *node* may be employed interchangeably in this article. However, we choose to use the term *node* preferentially within the context of networks, where nodes may realize operations, computations or would have some kind of agency, like in real-world networks. Thus, we choose to use the term *vertex* preferentially in the mathematical context of graph theory.

2.2. Algorithmic information theory. In this section, we briefly recover some of the main definitions in *algorithmic information* theory (aka Kolmogorov complexity theory or Solomonoff-Kolmogorov-Chaitin complexity theory) [7, 9, 17, 20].

Definition 2.8. Let $\{0, 1\}^*$ be the set of all finite binary strings.

Definition 2.9. Let $l(x)$ denote the length of a finite string $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$.² In addition, let $|X|$ denote the number of elements (i.e., the cardinality) in a set, if X is a finite set.

Definition 2.10. Let $(x)_2$ denote the string which is a binary representation of the number x . In addition, let $(x)_L$ denote the representation of the number $x \in \mathbb{N}$ in language L .

Definition 2.11. Let \mathbf{L}_U denote a binary universal programming language for a universal Turing machine U .

Definition 2.12. Let \mathbf{L}'_U denote a binary *prefix-free* (or *self-delimiting*) universal programming language for a prefix universal Turing machine U .

Definition 2.13. Let $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denote an arbitrary recursive bijective pairing function. This notation can be recursively extended to $\langle \cdot, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle \rangle$ and, then, to an ordered tuple $\langle \cdot, \cdot, \cdot \rangle$. This iteration can be recursively applied with the purpose of defining finite ordered tuples $\langle \cdot, \dots, \cdot \rangle$.

Definition 2.14. The (unconditional) *plain algorithmic complexity* (also known as C-complexity, plain Kolmogorov complexity, plain program-size complexity or plain Solomonoff-Kolmogorov-Chaitin complexity) of a finite binary string w , denoted by $C(w)$, is the length of the shortest program $w^* \in \mathbf{L}_U$ such that $U(w^*) = w$.³ The *conditional* plain algorithmic complexity of a binary finite string y given a binary finite string x , denoted by $C(y|x)$, is the length of the shortest program $w^* \in \mathbf{L}_U$ such that $U(\langle x, w^* \rangle) = y$. Note that $C(y) = C(y|\epsilon)$, where ϵ is the empty string. We also have the *joint* plain algorithmic complexity of strings x and y denoted by $C(x, y) := C(\langle x, y \rangle)$ and the *C-complexity of information* in x about y denoted by $I_C(x : y) := C(y) - C(y|x)$.

²In [17], $l(x)$ is denoted by $|x|$.

³Note that w^* denotes the lexicographically first $p \in \mathbf{L}_U$ such that $l(p)$ is minimum and $U(p) = w$.

Note 2.1. For an edge set $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$, let $C(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})) := C(\langle\langle\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})\rangle\rangle)$ denote

$$C(\langle\langle e_1, z_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle e_n, z_n \rangle \rangle)$$

such that

$$z_i = 1 \iff e_i \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}) ,$$

where $z_i \in \{0, 1\}$ with $1 \leq i \leq n = |\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G})|$. The same applies analogously to $C(E(G))$ and to the conditional, joint, and C-complexity of information cases.

Definition 2.15. The (unconditional) *prefix algorithmic complexity* (also known as K-complexity, prefix Kolmogorov complexity, prefix program-size complexity or prefix Solomonoff-Komogorov-Chaitin complexity) of a finite binary string w , denoted by $K(w)$, is the length of the shortest program $w^* \in \mathbf{L}'_{\mathbf{U}}$ such that $\mathbf{U}(w^*) = w$.⁴ The *conditional* prefix algorithmic complexity of a binary finite string y given a binary finite string x , denoted by $K(y|x)$, is the length of the shortest program $w^* \in \mathbf{L}'_{\mathbf{U}}$ such that $\mathbf{U}(\langle x, w^* \rangle) = y$. Note that $K(y) = K(y|\epsilon)$, where ϵ is the empty string. Similarly, we have the *joint* prefix algorithmic complexity of strings x and y denoted by $K(x, y) := K(\langle x, y \rangle)$, the *K-complexity of information* in x about y denoted by $I_K(x : y) := K(y) - K(y|x)$, and the *mutual algorithmic information* of the two strings x and y denoted by $I_A(x ; y) := K(y) - K(y|x^*)$.

Note 2.2. For an edge set $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$, let $K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})) := K(\langle\langle\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})\rangle\rangle)$ denote

$$K(\langle\langle e_1, z_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle e_n, z_n \rangle \rangle)$$

such that

$$z_i = 1 \iff e_i \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}) ,$$

where $z_i \in \{0, 1\}$ with $1 \leq i \leq n = |\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G})|$. The same applies analogously to $K(E(G))$ and to the conditional, joint, K-complexity of information, and mutual cases.

2.3. Algorithmically random multispect graphs. In order to study C-randomness (i.e., plain algorithmic randomness) of simple MAGs analogously to classical graphs, first we need to extend the concept of labeling in classical graphs to families of simple MAGs [1]:

Definition 2.16. A family $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c is *recursively labeled* iff there are programs $p'_1, p'_2 \in \{0, 1\}^*$ such that, for every $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ and for every $a_i, b_i, j \in \mathbb{N}$ with $1 \leq i \leq p \in \mathbb{N}$:

(I) if $(a_1, \dots, a_p), (b_1, \dots, b_p) \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$, then

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle\langle a_1, \dots, a_p \rangle, \langle b_1, \dots, b_p \rangle, p'_1 \rangle) = (j)_2$$

(II) if (a_1, \dots, a_p) or (b_1, \dots, b_p) does not belong to any $\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ with $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$, then

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle\langle a_1, \dots, a_p \rangle, \langle b_1, \dots, b_p \rangle, p'_1 \rangle) = 0$$

(III) if

$$1 \leq j \leq |\mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c)| = \frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|^2 - |\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{2} ,$$

then

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle\langle j, p'_2 \rangle) = \langle\langle a_1, \dots, a_p \rangle, \langle b_1, \dots, b_p \rangle \rangle = (e_j)_2$$

⁴ w^* denotes the lexicographically first $p \in \mathbf{L}'_{\mathbf{U}}$ such that $l(p)$ is minimum and $\mathbf{U}(p) = w$.

(IV) if

$$1 \leq j \leq |\mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c)| = \frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|^2 - |\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{2}$$

does not hold for any $\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ with $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$, then

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle j, \mathbf{p}'_2 \rangle) = \langle \langle a_1, \dots, a_p \rangle, \langle b_1, \dots, b_p \rangle \rangle = \langle 0 \rangle$$

Second, we extend the definition of plain algorithmically random classical graphs in [6, 20] to simple MAGs. In the classical graph case, we have in [6, 20]:

Definition 2.17. A classical graph G with $|V(G)| = n$ is $\delta(n)$ -C-random if, and only if, it satisfies

$$C(E(G) | n) \geq \binom{n}{2} - \delta(n)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \delta: \mathbb{N} &\rightarrow \mathbb{N} \\ n &\mapsto \delta(n) \end{aligned}$$

is the randomness deficiency function.

Therefore, in the simple MAG case, an analogous definition holds as introduced in [1]:

Definition 2.18. We say a simple MAG \mathcal{G}_c is $\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$ -C-random *iff* it satisfies

$$C(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \mid |\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) \geq \binom{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{2} - \delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \delta: \mathbb{N} &\rightarrow \mathbb{N} \\ n &\mapsto \delta(n) \end{aligned}$$

is the randomness deficiency function.

As introduced in [1], one can also apply this same concept of algorithmic randomness to the prefix-free (or self-delimited) version, i.e., K-randomness:

Definition 2.19. We say a simple MAG \mathcal{G}_c is $\mathbf{O}(1)$ -K-random *iff* it satisfies

$$K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) \geq \binom{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{2} - \mathbf{O}(1)$$

3. BACKGROUND RESULTS

In this section, we briefly recover some previous results in [1]. These are obtained from an extension of algorithmically random classical (i.e., labeled simple) graphs in [6, 20, 35, 37, 38] to multiaspect graphs [30, 31]. Thus, the definitions and notation on multiaspect graphs are based on [30, 31] and those on algorithmically random graphs are based on [6, 20, 35, 37, 38]. For a complete formalization and discussion on the definitions and notation, see also [1].

3.1. Algorithmic information theory. First of all, it is important to remember some basic and important relations in algorithmic information theory [8, 9, 17, 20].

Lemma 3.1. *For every $x, y \in \{0, 1\}^*$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$,*

- (1) $C(x) \leq l(x) + \mathbf{O}(1)$
- (2) $K(x) \leq l(x) + \mathbf{O}(\lg(l(x)))$
- (3) $C(y|x) \leq C(y) + \mathbf{O}(1)$
- (4) $K(y|x) \leq K(y) + \mathbf{O}(1)$
- (5) $C(y|x) \leq K(y|x) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq C(y|x) + \mathbf{O}(\lg(C(y|x)))$
- (6) $C(x) \leq C(x, y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq C(y) + C(x|y) + \mathbf{O}(\lg(C(x, y)))$
- (7) $K(x) \leq K(x, y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq K(y) + K(x|y) + \mathbf{O}(1)$
- (8) $C(x) \leq K(x) + \mathbf{O}(1)$
- (9) $K(n) = \mathbf{O}(\lg(n))$
- (10) $K(x) \leq C(x) + K(C(x)) + \mathbf{O}(1)$
- (11) $I_A(x; y) = I_A(y; x) \pm \mathbf{O}(1)$

Note that the inverse relation $K(x, y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \geq K(y) + K(x|y) + \mathbf{O}(1)$ does not hold in general in Equation (7). In fact, one can show that $K(x, y) = K(y) + K(x|y, K(y)) \pm \mathbf{O}(1)$, which is the key step to prove Equation (11). In this way, we have that the notion of *network topological (algorithmic) information* of a simple MAG \mathcal{G}_c , i.e., the irreducible information necessary to determine/compute $\langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle$, is formally captured by $I_A(\langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle; \langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle) = K(\langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle) \pm \mathbf{O}(1)$. In the present article, wherever the concept of information is mentioned, we are in fact referring to algorithmic information.

3.2. Multiaspect graphs and graphs isomorphism. In order to represent multidimensional networks, we are basing our work on a generalized graph representation of dyadic relations between n -tuples [30, 31] called multiaspect graphs (MAGs). Directly from [30], one has that a simple MAG is basically equivalent to a classical (i.e., simple labeled) graph:

Corollary 3.1. *For every simple MAG \mathcal{G}_c of order $p > 0$, where all aspects are non-empty sets, there is a unique (up to a graph isomorphism) classical graph $G_{\mathcal{G}_c} = (V, E)$ with $|V(G)| = \prod_{n=1}^p |\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[n]|$ that is isomorphic to \mathcal{G}_c .*

We also have that the concepts of *walk*, *trail*, and *path* become well-defined for MAGs analogously to within the context of graphs. See Section 3.5 in [30].

3.3. Algorithmically random multiaspect graphs. In order to study *plain* algorithmic randomness (i.e., C-randomness) of simple MAGs, we extended in [1] the concept of labeling in classical graphs to simple MAGs. Then, we directly extended the definition of plain algorithmically random (i.e., $\delta(|V(G)|)$ -C-random) classical graphs to simple MAGs. Thus, by combining Corollary 3.1 with well-known inequalities in algorithmic information theory [9, 17, 20], we showed that:

Theorem 3.1. *Let $F_{\mathcal{G}_c} \neq \emptyset$ be an arbitrary recursively labeled family of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c . Then, for every $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$*

\mathcal{G}_c is $(\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)))$ -C-random
iff

G is $(\delta(|V(G)|) + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G)|)))$ -C-random

where G is isomorphic (as in Definition 2.6) to \mathcal{G}_c .

The existence of such recursively labeled infinite families also follows from [1] (see also Lemma 3.3 and Theorem 3.2):

Lemma 3.2. *There is a recursively labeled infinite family $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c with arbitrary symmetric adjacency matrix such that every one of them has the same order p .*

In addition, it is shown in [1] that the binary string that determines the presence or absence of a composite edge in Definition 2.4 can be properly defined for recursively labeled families:

Corollary 3.2. *Let $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ be a recursively labeled family of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c . Then, for every $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ and $x \in \{0,1\}^*$, where x is the characteristic string of \mathcal{G}_c , the following relations hold:*

$$(12) \quad C(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) | x) \leq K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) | x) + \mathbf{O}(1) = \mathbf{O}(1)$$

$$(13) \quad C(x | \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) \leq K(x | \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) + \mathbf{O}(1) = \mathbf{O}(1)$$

$$(14) \quad K(x) = K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) \pm \mathbf{O}(1)$$

$$(15) \quad I_A(x; \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) = I_A(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c); x) \pm \mathbf{O}(1) = K(x) - \mathbf{O}(1) = K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) \pm \mathbf{O}(1)$$

In summary, Theorem 3.1 shows that the plain algorithmic complexity of simple MAGs and of its respective isomorphic classical graphs are roughly the same, except for the amount of algorithmic information necessary to encode the length of the program that performs this isomorphism on an arbitrary universal Turing machine. In fact, regarding the connections through composite edges, this shows that not only “most” of the network topological properties of G are inherited by \mathcal{G}_c (and vice-versa), but also “most” of its topological incompressibility (i.e., the incompressibility of $\langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle$). That is, more formally, every network topological property (regarding the connections through composite edges) that derives from \mathcal{G}_c being $(\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)))$ -C-random will be inherited by \mathcal{G}_c from G , if G is $(\delta(|V(G)|) + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G)|)))$ -C-random and $|V(G)|$ is large enough. And the inverse inheritance also holds. For example, we extended in [1] some results from [6, 20] on plain algorithmically random classical graphs to simple MAGs:

Corollary 3.3. *Let $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ be an arbitrary recursively labeled infinite family of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c . Then, the following hold for large enough $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$:*

- (1) *The degree $\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{v})$ of a composite vertex $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ in a $\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$ -C-random MAG $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ satisfies*

$$\left| \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{v}) - \left(\frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| - 1}{2} \right) \right| = \mathbf{O} \left(\sqrt{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| (\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)))} \right)$$

- (2) *$\mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$ -C-random MAGs $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ have*

$$\frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{4} \pm \mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$$

disjoint paths of length 2 between each pair of composite vertices $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$. In particular, $\mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$ - C -random MAGs $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ have composite diameter 2.

Thus, an incompressible simple MAG under randomness deficiency $\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) = \mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$ tends to be an expected ‘almost regular’ graph in the limit when the network size increases indefinitely; for sufficiently large set of composite vertices, these MAGs also cross a phase transition in which the diameter between composite vertices becomes 2; with respect to k -connectivity, as defined in [6], they are $\frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{4} \pm \mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$ -connected. Furthermore, from Definition 2.19, one can build an infinite family of simple MAGs in which every member is $\mathbf{O}(1)$ - K -random and, in turn, also retrieve their plain algorithmically randomness [1]:

Lemma 3.3. *There is a recursively labeled infinite family $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c that are $\mathbf{O}(1)$ - K -random.*

Theorem 3.2. *Let $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ be a recursively labeled infinite family of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c such that, for every $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, if $x \upharpoonright_n$ is its characteristic string and $n = |\mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}_c)|$, then $x \in [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$ is $\mathbf{O}(1)$ - K -random. Thus, every MAG $\mathcal{G}_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ is $\mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|))$ - C -random and $\mathbf{O}(1)$ - K -random. In addition, there is such a family $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ with $\Omega = x \in [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$, where Ω is the halting probability [7, 9].*

4. SNAPSHOT-LIKE MULTIDIMENSIONAL NETWORKS

This section presents a theoretical investigation of the consequences of the results in Section 3.3 to some of the common representations of dynamic networks and multilayer networks. As we will explain and formalize in Section 4.2, we choose a differential approach to the dynamic and multilayer case, so that both become particular cases of general multidimensional networks while keeping their own distinct physical interpretation of what each ‘dimension’ (or aspect) [30–32] represents. In this way, we first present the investigation of the algorithmic complexity of snapshot-based representations of dynamic networks. Then, in Section 4.2, we introduce the same kind of investigation for multiplex networks.

4.1. Snapshot-dynamic networks. In the context of real-world complex networks analysis, one may highlight some important representation models of dynamic networks, such as, time-varying graphs (TVGs) [11, 30, 31, 34], temporal networks (TNs) [24, 27], temporal graphs (TGs) [21], and snapshot networks (SNs) [27, 34]. In this direction, we follow the same unifying and universal approach in [34] with the purpose of showing that a particular class of dynamic networks (in the case, snapshot-dynamic networks) displays less irreducible information content than a more general representation of dynamic networks such as TVGs. However, studying the advantages and disadvantages of each representation model in terms of network analysis is not in our current scope. Thus, we focus on studying a general snapshot-based representation of dynamic networks and its algorithmic randomness in relation to time-varying graphs (TVGs) and its algorithmic randomness. Note that TVGs are second order multispect graphs (MAGs) [11, 33, 34].

The main idea is to: first, briefly discuss equivalences of some of the main representations of snapshot-like dynamic networks; secondly, study the algorithmic randomness of snapshot-dynamic networks, which can be represented by a particular class of TVGs; and, then, compare with the algorithmic randomness of general

undirected dynamic networks, which are arbitrary simple TVGs, i.e., second order simple MAGs.

Except for the cases in which the pertinence of the vertices in each time instant (and not only its connectivity in each time instant) do matter in the network analysis—see node-alignment below—, one can easily show that a snapshot-based representation as in [27] is equivalent to the snapshot-based representation in [34]. To this end, note that, in [27], a snapshot network is defined as a sequence of graphs $G_i = (V_i, E_i)$ in the form $(G_0, \dots, G_{t_{max}})$. On the other hand, in [34], a snapshot network is a TVG composed of only *spatial* edges, i.e., edges that connect two vertices at the same time instant only. In other words, a snapshot-like dynamic network in [34] is a special case of dynamic network that can be solely represented by, for example, the main diagonal blocks of the adjacency matrix of the isomorphic graph to the TVG in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. The adjacency matrix of the isomorphic graph to the TVG, which represents a sequentially coupled node-aligned dynamic network.

For the sake of simplicity, we call an arbitrary TVG $G_t = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ composed of only *spatial* edges as a *spatial* TVG. Therefore, the sequence of vertex sets $(V_0, \dots, V_{t_{max}})$ in $G_i = (V_i, E_i)$ may be mapped onto a larger vertex set

$$V = \bigcup_{V_i \in (V_0, \dots, V_{t_{max}})} V_i$$

such that $G_t = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$, $|\{G_i | G_i \in (G_0, \dots, G_{t_{max}})\}| = |T(G_t)|$, and

$$(16) \quad (u, v) \in E_i(G_i) \iff (u, t_i, v, t_i) \in \mathcal{E}(G_t),$$

where $0 \leq i \leq t_{max}$. Inversely, a spatial TVG can be univocally represented by a sequence of graphs $(G_0, \dots, G_{t_{max}})$ as in [27] by simply assuming $V_i = V_j$ for every $0 \leq i \leq t_{max}$ and $0 \leq j \leq t_{max}$, so that the equivalence in Equation (16) also holds.

In most cases, a *node-alignment* [12, 18] hypothesis (i.e., $V_i = V_j$ for every $0 \leq i \leq t_{max}$ and $0 \leq j \leq t_{max}$) is assumed, so that no additional information would be needed to determine which vertices do not belong to a specific time instant. Thus, for the present purposes of this article, we assume that the snapshot network is

node-aligned. Nevertheless, an interesting future research would be to investigate the worst-case scenarios in which additional information is needed to recover the original snapshot network that is not node-aligned from the spatial TVG. Indeed, an irreducible information dependency on the sequence $(V \setminus V_0, \dots, V \setminus V_{t_{max}})$ of excluded vertices may take place in a similar manner to the one on the companion tuple in [1, Theorem 3.1]. In any event, note that retrieving the correspondent spatial TVG [30, 34] from the snapshot network [27] is always straightforward by the addition of *empty nodes* [18] (or, in MAG terminology, unconnected composite vertices [31]), since every TVG is defined on the set of composite vertices [30] and, therefore, is always node-aligned by definition.

Another formalization of a snapshot-like dynamic network may be through restricting the set $\mathbb{E}(G_t)$ of all possible composite edges of a TVG G_t into another set $\mathbb{E}'(G_t)$ such that, for every $e \in \mathbb{E}(G_t)$ and $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$e = (u, t_i, v, t_j) \in \mathbb{E}'(G_t) \iff j = f(i) ,$$

where $f : \{0, f(0), f(f(0)), \dots, f^{-1}(|T(G_t)| - 1)\} \rightarrow \{f(0), f(f(0)), \dots, |T(G_t)| - 1\}$ is a strictly increasing bijective function defined on any recursive iteration. Thus, these restricted TVGs $G_t = (V, \mathcal{E}', T)$, where $\mathcal{E}'(G_t) \subseteq \mathbb{E}'(G_t)$, may present advantages when considering a more realistic scenario in which relations or communications between nodes are not instantaneous or demand non-equal time intervals over time. In addition, if one allows *temporal edges* (i.e., edges connecting the same node at two distinct time instants [34]), which are directly analogous to *coupling edges* [18] in the multilayer case, some assumptions like the one that guarantees the transitivity on a node in the case it is disconnected within one or more snapshots become unnecessary.

In fact, unlike the multilayer case in which there may not be a physical interpretation of the necessity of preserving the pairwise ordering of layers—as we will also discuss in Section 4.2—, this assumption of transitivity is represented by a restriction on the set of temporal (or coupling) edges: we say a TVG is *sequentially coupled* if all the temporal (or coupling) edges are connecting the same node u from the time instant t_i to the time instant t_{i+1} only and, for every $0 \leq i \leq t_{max}$, every node u has a temporal (or coupling) edge to itself from the time instant t_i to the time instant t_{i+1} . The reader is invited to note that sequentially coupling is an even stronger restriction of the set of coupling edges than saying that the couplings are *diagonal* and/or *categorical* as in [18]—see also Section 4.2. That is, if the network is sequentially coupled, there is *no* other temporal (or coupling) edge connecting a node u at time instant t_i to the same node u at time instant t_j than the case in which $j = i + 1$. An example of sequentially coupled networks are the temporal networks as defined in [5], should they be also node-aligned.

Thus, one can see that a snapshot-like dynamic network in the form (V, \mathcal{E}', T) enables one to better represent the cases in which the sequential coupling does not hold in general; or, in other words, in which some nodes may not relay information for future communication in forthcoming time instants. Related to this issue, it is a consequence of the result we will demonstrate in Section 5 that arbitrary incompressible simple TVGs are not sequentially coupled. See Corollary 5.2. This representation of snapshot-like dynamic networks in the form (V, \mathcal{E}', T) can also be reduced to spatial TVGs (V, \mathcal{E}, T'') —i.e., without the restrictions in the

set of composite edges—by injectively mapping the set of time intervals onto another set $T''(G_t)$ of time instants while preserving the previous ordering: for example, one runs a recursive bijective procedure that makes $t_i'' \equiv (t_i, t_{f(i)})$, where $|T''(G_t)| \leq |T(G_t)| - 1$, and

$$e = (u, t_i, v, t_{f(i)}) \in \mathbb{E}'(G_t) \iff (u, t_i'', v, t_i'') \in \mathcal{E}(G_t)$$

Again, as also occurred for snapshot networks $(G_0, \dots, G_{t_{max}})$, retrieving the spatial TVG from a snapshot-like dynamic network (V, \mathcal{E}', T) is straightforward, whereas the inverse conversion may require additional information, in particular to determine which is the time interval $(t_i, t_{f(i)})$ that each t_i'' is representing (in the case these intervals are not uniformly equal). Thus, a future investigation of the worst-case information dependency of a non-uniform function $f(i)$ will be necessary; and the irreducible topological information (i.e., the irreducible information necessary to determine/compute $\langle \mathcal{E}' \rangle$) carried by an arbitrary (V, \mathcal{E}', T) may be less compressible than that of spatial TVGs.

In this way, for the purposes of this article, we assume hereafter the representation of a snapshot-like dynamic network as a spatial TVG; and we call them simply as *snapshot-dynamic network*. Note that underlying properties in snapshot-dynamic networks, like the sequential coupling, are fixed and the presence of such composite edges are always recursively decidable from the composite vertices' labels. Therefore, the algorithmic information of a spatial TVG and the algorithmic information of a spatial TVG with the addition of sequential couplings can only differ by a constant (that only depends on the chosen language $\mathbf{L}_{\mathcal{U}}$) and, thus, is negligible in our forthcoming results.

It is straightforward to calculate the maximum number of spatial directed edges $e \in \mathcal{E}(G_t)$ in a *traditional* TVG $G_t^d = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$. Note that a *traditional* MAG is a (directed or undirected) MAG without (composite) self-loops [1, 30]. Moreover, from [11, 34], we have that a TVG is a second order MAG. Therefore, we define a *traditional directed* TVG $G_t^d = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ as a TVG without (spatio-temporal [34]) self-loops. This way, we will have that there are

$$|T(G_t^d)| \left(|V(G_t^d)|^2 - |V(G_t^d)| \right)$$

possible spatial directed edges.

From a simple graph (i.e., an undirected graph without self-loops) perspective, we may consider spatial TVGs as sequences of simple graphs. We call a *simple* TVG $G_t^u = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ as a particular case of a simple second order MAG, where a simple MAG is defined in [1] as a traditional *undirected* MAG. This way, we will have that there are

$$|T(G_t^u)| \left(\frac{|V(G_t^u)|^2 - |V(G_t^u)|}{2} \right)$$

possible spatial undirected edges in *simple spatial* TVGs.

Now, let G'_t denote an arbitrary simple spatial TVG $G'_t = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ that belongs to a *recursively labeled* infinite family $F_{G'_t}$ of arbitrary simple TVGs. The existence of such a family is guaranteed by Lemma 3.2. Directly from Definiton 2.4, we have the binary string that univocally represents the presence or absence of an edge in $\mathcal{E}(G'_t)$; and we call it the *characteristic string* of G'_t [1]. In this sense, from Corollary 3.2, one can see that a characteristic string promptly contains all the information that is necessary to computably retrieve the entire G'_t , except for

the information required to apply a previously known recursive way to label the composite vertices and order the composite edges. In fact, as shown in [1], this exception shall be taken into account for MAGs in general. This occurs because, for certain multidimensional networks that can only be represented by a MAG with a high enough order—note that the order of a MAG is defined as the number of aspects [30]—, the information necessary to compute $\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ from a characteristic string x may be dominated by the information necessary to define the sizes and the ordering of the dimensions (in the case of MAGs, the aspects). See [1, Theorem 3.1].

It is also important to note that the information encoded in the characteristic string may be displaying a decompressed form of its algorithmic information content. To tackle this issue, we define the algorithmic-informational version of the characteristic string, and thus formalizing such a notion of topological (algorithmic) information—see Theorem 4.1, Corollary 3.2, and Section 3.1—that is potentially agnostic with respect to node labeling or indexing:

Definition 4.1. Let $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ be a recursively labeled family of simple MAGs \mathcal{G}_c . Let $p_1'', p_2'' \in \mathbf{L}_U$ be fixed and only depend on $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$. We say a binary string $y \in \{0, 1\}^*$ is an *algorithmically characteristic string* of \mathcal{G}_c with respect to $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$ iff $\mathbf{U}(\langle y, p_1'' \rangle) = \langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle$ and $\mathbf{U}(\langle \langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle, p_2'' \rangle) = y$.

Thus, if y is such an algorithmically characteristic string, it is immediate to show that

$$C(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)|y) \leq K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)|y) + \mathbf{O}(1) = \mathbf{O}(1)$$

and

$$C(y|\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) \leq K(y|\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) + \mathbf{O}(1) = \mathbf{O}(1)$$

hold independently of the choice of \mathcal{G}_c in $F_{\mathcal{G}_c}$. On the other hand, it may not be the case that the opposite implication (i.e.,

$$K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)|y) + \mathbf{O}(1) = \mathbf{O}(1)$$

and

$$K(y|\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) + \mathbf{O}(1) = \mathbf{O}(1)$$

implying the existence of constants $p_1'', p_2'' \in \mathbf{L}_U$ such that $\mathbf{U}(\langle y, p_1'' \rangle) = \langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle$ and $\mathbf{U}(\langle \langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle, p_2'' \rangle) = y$ does hold in general—and this should be an interesting future research. For example, a possible question in this direction might be whether it is possible or not to construct a recursively labeled infinite family of MAGs in which there is an infinite subfamily of MAGs that are K-trivial [17], but not computable, with respect to a string y .

In any event, from the proof of Corollary 3.2 presented in [1], we have that Definition 4.1 is always satisfiable by taking the algorithmically characteristic string y as, for instance, the very characteristic string. This holds because of the recursively labeling of the entire family of MAGs, as in Definition 2.16. However, since one surely knows there are

$$\left(\frac{(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2 - |V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)}{2} \right) - |T(G'_t)| \left(\frac{|V(G'_t)|^2 - |V(G'_t)|}{2} \right)$$

non-existent non-spatial undirected edges (including non-spatial undirected edges that are sequential couplings) and G'_t is a second order simple MAG \mathcal{G}_c , one can

compress the characteristic string of G'_t in such a way that the resulting algorithmically characteristic string retains the algorithmic information carried, or conveyed, by the usual characteristic string:

Theorem 4.1. *Let $G'_t = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ be a simple spatial TVG that belongs to a recursively labeled infinite family $F_{G'_t}$ of simple TVGs. Then, there is a binary string $y \in \{0, 1\}^*$ that is an algorithmically characteristic string of G'_t such that*

$$K(y) \leq l(y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq |T(G'_t)| \left(\frac{|V(G'_t)|^2 - |V(G'_t)|}{2} \right) + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)) ,$$

$$K(x) \leq K(y) + \mathbf{O}(1) ,$$

$$K(x | y^*) \leq K(x | y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \mathbf{O}(1) ,$$

$$K(y) \leq K(x) + \mathbf{O}(1) ,$$

and

$$K(y | x^*) \leq K(y | x) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \mathbf{O}(1)$$

hold, where x is the characteristic string of G'_t .

Proof. The main idea of the proof is based on showing a Turing equivalence between the string y and its respective characteristic string x . Then, as in the proof of Corollary 3.2 presented in [1], we will recover the Turing equivalence between the characteristic string x and the string $\langle \mathcal{E}(G'_t) \rangle$. So, first let $y' \in \{0, 1\}^*$ be any arbitrary binary string with

$$l(y') = |T(G'_t)| \left(\frac{|V(G'_t)|^2 - |V(G'_t)|}{2} \right)$$

Let $p'_2 \in \{0, 1\}^*$ be a binary string that represents an algorithm running on a prefix universal Turing machine \mathbf{U} that takes $j \in \mathbb{N}$ as input and returns the j -th edge in $\mathbb{E}_c(G'_t)$. The existence of such p'_2 is guaranteed by the definition of recursively labeling in [1] (see Definition 2.16). Moreover, p'_2 is independent of the choice of G'_t in the family $F_{G'_t}$. Let $s_1 \in \{0, 1\}^*$ be a binary string that represents an algorithm running on a prefix universal Turing machine \mathbf{U} that:

- (1) takes p'_2 , y' and j as inputs;
- (2) calculates $\mathbf{U}(\langle j', p'_2 \rangle)$ for every $j' \leq j$;
- (3) enumerates all the spatial edges $e_{j'} = \mathbf{U}(\langle j', p'_2 \rangle)$ as a subsequence of the sequence of possible undirected edges in (e_1, \dots, e_j) ;
- (4) and returns:⁵
 - (a) 0, if $\mathbf{U}(\langle j, p'_2 \rangle)$ is not a spatial edge;
 - (b) 1, if $\mathbf{U}(\langle j, p'_2 \rangle)$ is the i -th spatial edge and the i -th digit in y' is 1;
 - (c) 0, if $\mathbf{U}(\langle j, p'_2 \rangle)$ is the i -th spatial edge and the i -th digit in y' is 0.

Note that deciding whether an edge e is spatial or not follows directly from deciding whether $t_u = t_v$ or not in $e = (u, t_u, v, t_v)$, which is a decidable (and computationally cheap) procedure. Let $s_2 \in \{0, 1\}^*$ be a binary string that represents an algorithm running on a prefix universal Turing machine \mathbf{U} that:

⁵Alternatively, in the case the sequential couplings were not excluded in the representation of the snapshot-dynamic network, one can add here a clause also returning 1 if $\mathbf{U}(\langle j, p'_2 \rangle)$ is a sequential coupling. The reader is invited to note that the theorem holds anyway.

(1) takes s_1, p'_2, y' and

$$\left(\frac{(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2 - |V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|}{2} \right)$$

as inputs;

(2) calculates $\mathbf{U}(\langle j, y', p'_2, s_1 \rangle)$ for every j with

$$1 \leq j \leq \left(\frac{(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2 - |V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|}{2} \right) ;$$

(3) and returns the binary string

$$x = z_1 \dots z_n$$

such that

$$z_i = 1 \iff \mathbf{U}(\langle i, y', p'_2, s_1 \rangle) = 1 ,$$

$$\text{where } z_i \in \{0, 1\} \text{ with } 1 \leq i \leq n = \left(\frac{(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2 - |V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|}{2} \right) .$$

Now, let $y = \langle k, y', p'_2, s_1, s_2 \rangle$, where k is the self-delimiting binary representation of

$$\left(\frac{(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2 - |V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|}{2} \right) \in \mathbb{N} .$$

We know one can encode k in $\mathbf{O}(\log_2((|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2))$ bits. Therefore, since p'_2, s_1 , and s_2 are fixed and independent of the choice of G'_t , we will have that, by the minimality of the prefix algorithmic complexity,

$$\begin{aligned} K(x) &\leq K(y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq l(\langle k, y', p'_2, s_1, s_2 \rangle) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \\ &\leq l(y') + \mathbf{O}(\log_2((|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2)) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$K(x | y^*) \leq K(x | y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \mathbf{O}(1) .$$

On the other hand, in order to show that $K(y) \leq K(x) + \mathbf{O}(1)$, let $s_3 \in \{0, 1\}^*$ be a binary string that represents an algorithm running on a prefix universal Turing machine \mathbf{U} that:

- (1) takes p'_2, s_1, s_2 , and x as inputs;
- (2) enumerates all the spatial edges using program p'_2 ;
- (3) and builds the binary string $y' = y'_1 \dots y'_{k'}$ such that:
 - (a) $y'_i = 1$, if j corresponds to the i -th spatial edge and the j -th digit of x is 1;
 - (b) $y'_i = 0$, if j corresponds to the i -th spatial edge and the j -th digit of x is 0;
- (4) finally, s_3 returns the binary string $\langle k, y', p'_2, s_1, s_2 \rangle = y$.

Note that x was already given as input and

$$l(x) = \left(\frac{(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)^2 - |V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|}{2} \right) .$$

Therefore, since p'_2, s_1, s_2 , and s_3 are fixed and independent of the choice of G'_t , we will have that, by the minimality of the prefix algorithmic complexity,

$$K(y) = K(\langle k, y', p'_2, s_1, s_2 \rangle) \leq K(\langle x, p'_2, s_1, s_2, s_3 \rangle) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq K(x) + \mathbf{O}(1)$$

and

$$K(y | x^*) \leq K(y | x) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \mathbf{O}(1)$$

Now, let p be a binary string that represents the algorithm running on a universal Turing machine that:

- (1) receives the string x as its input;
- (2) for $1 \leq j \leq l(x)$, reads each j -th bit of x ;
- (3) calculates $\mathbf{U}(\langle j, p'_2 \rangle)$;
- (4) and, from the outputs e_j of these programs $\langle j, p'_2 \rangle$, returns the string $\langle \langle e_1, z_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle e_n, z_n \rangle \rangle$, where: $z_j = 1$, if the j -th bit of x is 1; and $z_j = 0$, if the j -th bit of x is 0.

Thus, since p'_2 is fixed, we will have that there is a self-delimiting binary encoding of p such that

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle x, p \rangle) = \langle \langle e_1, z_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle e_n, z_n \rangle \rangle$$

holds. Then, by the minimality of $K(\cdot)$, we will have that

$$K(\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) | x) \leq l(p) \leq \mathbf{O}(1)$$

Analogously to program p , using program p'_1 instead of p'_2 in order to build the string x from $\langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle$, we will have another program q such that there is a self-delimiting binary encoding of q such that

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle \langle \langle e_1, z_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle e_n, z_n \rangle \rangle, q \rangle) = x$$

holds and, by the minimality of $K(\cdot)$, we have that

$$K(x | \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)) \leq l(q) \leq \mathbf{O}(1)$$

Note that $p, q, p'_1, p'_2, s_1, s_2, s_3$ are fixed. Therefore, in order to finish the proof, just let p''_1 be the binary string that represents the algorithm running on a universal Turing machine \mathbf{U} that receives y as input and returns the value of

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle \mathbf{U}(y), p \rangle) = \langle \langle e_1, z_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle e_n, z_n \rangle \rangle = \langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle .$$

Similarly, let p''_2 be the binary string that represents the algorithm running on a universal Turing machine \mathbf{U} that receives $\langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle$ as input and returns the value of

$$\mathbf{U}(\langle \mathbf{U}(\langle \langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) \rangle), q \rangle, p'_2, s_1, s_2, s_3) = y .$$

□

Thus, for every simple spatial TVG $G'_t = (V, \mathcal{E}, T)$ that belongs to a *recursively labeled* infinite family $F_{C'_t}$ of simple TVGs, we will have that, from Lemma 3.1, Theorem 4.1, and Corollary 3.2,

$$\begin{aligned} C\left(\mathcal{E}(G'_t) \mid (|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)\right) &\leq K(\mathcal{E}(G'_t)) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \\ &\leq |T(G'_t)| \left(\frac{|V(G'_t)|^2 - |V(G'_t)|}{2} \right) \\ &\quad + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)) \end{aligned}$$

holds.⁶ On the other hand, as shown in [1], we directly have from Lemma 3.3, Corollary 3.2, and Theorem 3.2 that, for arbitrary $\mathbf{O}(1)$ -K-random simple TVGs

⁶In fact, one can even improve this inequality to show that $C(\mathcal{E}(G'_t) \mid (|V(G'_t)| |T(G'_t)|)) \leq \mathbf{O}\left(|T(G'_t)| \left(\frac{|V(G'_t)|^2 - |V(G'_t)|}{2} \right)\right)$.

G_t ,

$$K(\mathcal{E}(G_t)) \geq \left(\frac{(|V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|)^2 - |V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|}{2} \right) - \mathbf{O}(1)$$

and

$$C(\mathcal{E}(G_t) \mid (|V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|)) \geq \left(\frac{(|V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|)^2 - |V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|}{2} \right) - \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|)) .$$

Therefore, for large enough sets of time instants, $\mathbf{O}(1)$ -K-random simple TVGs carry at least

$$\left(\frac{(|V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|)^2 - |V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|}{2} \right) - |T(G_t)| \left(\frac{|V(G_t)|^2 - |V(G_t)|}{2} \right) - \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G_t)| |T(G_t)|))$$

more topological (or network) irreducible information than any simple spatial TVG could carry.

4.2. Multiplex networks. Other network models of increasing importance in network science are those in which the nodes and/or connections between nodes may have distinct features [5, 10, 13, 14, 18, 19, 30–32] other than the time dependency. For example, one may differentiate, in the case of:

- social networks,
 - between connection features, such as friendship, family, professional colleagues, face-to-face interaction, email interaction, etc [10, 12, 18];
 - or between node features, such as gender, online platform, school, city, company, etc [10, 18];
- biological networks,
 - between connection features, such as distinct nature of protein-protein reactions [14], neuronal interactions (in particular, either through chemical or ionic channels) [5], etc;
 - or between node features, such as distinct species, gene pool, community, location [25], etc;
- multimodal transportation networks,
 - between connection features, such as bus network, the subway network, the air transportation network [19, 29], etc;
 - or between node features, such as airline companies [29], etc.

Usually in the modeling of complex networked systems, each of these features has been called a *layer* [5, 18, 29, 31]. Particularly, in this section, we focus on connection features, analyzing the theoretical characteristics of the so called *multiplex* networks [12, 18], which are a type of multilayer network. We first briefly discuss some representation equivalences. Then, we apply an analogous investigation to that of Section 4.1.

Before presenting multiplex networks, it is important to recover some definitions and nomenclatures from the previous literature on the subject, clarifying conditions or assumptions behind the mathematical concepts, so as to enable unambiguous applications of our theoretical results in future studies of real-world networks. In doing so, we are not only grounding our nomenclature on, but also following the same purpose of terminology unification in [18]. In this way, we choose an approach in

order that one can distinguish between multilayer networks and dynamic networks, even though both can be viewed as just distinct physical interpretations of the same kind of network's aspect (or dimension).

To this end, we compare a well-known definition of multilayer network as in [18] with the multidimensional (i.e., high-order) approach formalized in [30, 31]. In [18] (or, equivalently, in [5]), a *multilayer* network $M = (V_M, E_M, V, \mathbf{L})$ is understood as an interconnected and/or intraconnected labeled collection of graphs. Each of these graphs represents a 'layer' whose (distinct or not) vertex sets can be either linked within this 'layer' or linked to a vertex in another 'layer'. Formally, a multilayer network $M = (V_M, E_M, V, \mathbf{L})$ [18] is defined by:

- V denotes the set of all possible vertices v ;
- $\mathbf{L} = \{L_a\}_{a=1}^d$ denotes a collection of $d \in \mathbb{N}$ sets L_a composed of *elementary layers* $\alpha \in L_a$;
- $V_M \subseteq V \times L_1 \times \dots \times L_d$ denotes the subset of all possible vertices that belong to a 'layer' $L_1 \times \dots \times L_d$;
- $E_M \subseteq V_M \times V_M$ denotes the set of *interlayer* and/or *intralayer* edges connecting two *node-layer tuples* $(v, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d) \in V_M$.

An interlayer edge is defined as $((u, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d), (v, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_d)) \in E_M$ such that $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d) \neq (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_d)$ and an intralayer is defined as $((u, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d), (v, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_d)) \in E_M$ such that $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d) = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_d)$. In addition, one defines a *coupling* edge $((u, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d), (v, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_d)) \in E_M$ as an interlayer edge with $u = v$.

Actually, there are in fact some equivalences between a MAG [30] (see Definition 2.1) and a multilayer $M = (V_M, E_M, V, \mathbf{L})$: V is the usual set of vertices $V(\mathcal{G}) \equiv \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[1]$; each set L_a is the a -th aspect $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[a]$ of a MAG \mathcal{G} ; V_M is a subset of the set of all composite vertices $\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G})$, where a node-layer tuple $(v, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_d) \in V_M$ is a composite vertex $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G})$; $E_M \equiv \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$ is a subset of the set of all composite edges $\mathbb{E}(\mathcal{G})$. The only distinctive characteristic of $M = (V_M, E_M, V, \mathbf{L})$ and $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{E})$ is the possibility that one or more vertices do not belong to one or more aspects of a MAG. Therefore, if a multilayer network M is node-aligned [12, 18], i.e., $V_M = V \times L_1 \times \dots \times L_d$, this multilayer network M is equivalent to a $(d+1)$ -order MAG. Thus, a node-aligned multilayer network with d layers is a network that can be mathematically represented by a $(d+1)$ -order MAG.

In most cases, as mentioned in Section 4.1, a node-alignment hypothesis can be assumed [18], except for the cases in which the pertinence of the vertices in each layer (and not only its connectivity) do matter in the network analysis. In this regard, we also leave as future research the investigation of the worst cases for the information needed to retrieve V_M from $V \times L_1 \times \dots \times L_d$. Due to this possibility, the algorithmic information carried by M may be larger than that of the correspondent MAG \mathcal{G} with $d+1$ aspects and $E_M = \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$. Anyway, for the purposes of the present article, we assume hereafter that the multilayer networks M are node-aligned, so that $\langle E_M \rangle$ denotes the string $\langle \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}) \rangle$ with respect to such correspondent MAG \mathcal{G} , where $E_M := \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G})$.

Besides the above formalities, we choose a distinguishing interpretation of the two currently studied multidimensional structures in complex networks: dynamism and "multilayerism".⁷ In accordance with [29–31], and unlike [5, 13, 18] (where dynamic networks are considered as a particular type of multilayer networks), we are

⁷And this distinction will be reflected in our nomenclature and in our notation.

considering a time-varying graph topology, like in dynamic networks in Section 4.1, and a multilayer topology, like the ones of the above described M , as two distinct multidimensional structures.

At a first glance, both the mathematical representations of a finite time progression and of a finite number of different layers can be performed by an ordered set of labels (or indexes). However, besides distinct physical properties, a multilayer network may not need to obey a sequential indexing of layers that corresponds to a meaningful ordering of the physical counterparts of each layer. This promptly differs from the sequential coupling introduced in Section 4.1. For example, node features (e.g., species, gender, or company) or connection features (e.g., bus network or email interaction) in the multilayer case do not have an intrinsic underlying structure that indicates the direction that the information is ‘flowing through’ an edge, whereas the opposite holds in principle for time instants in dynamic networks. Moreover, as we will show in Section 5, some topological properties, such as the presence of crosslayer edges, may happen to make sense in multilayer networks, whereas, in dynamic networks—specially, in snapshot-dynamic networks—, some topological properties, such as the presence of transtemporal edges, do not.

In addition, we are assuming a general meaning of the nomenclature ‘multidimensional’ so as to encompass both each individual node (or connection) feature⁸ and each type of the individual node (or connection) features. We say that each type of individual feature, such as being an arbitrary time instant or being an arbitrary layer, is a *node dimension*. Thus, a node dimension corresponds to an aspect of a MAG, as in [29–31]. This is in consonance with a common understanding of a dimension as being an aspect or property in which a particular object can assume different values, names, etc.

However, note that this differs from some usages of the term in the literature of network science, where for example one may say that a node u linked to a node v through a family relation lies on a different ‘dimension’ than that of a node u' linked to a node v' through a professional relation. In this sense, the particular object that can assume different values is the connection itself and the different values are the nodes. This way, any element of an aspect of a MAG other than the set of vertices represents a ‘dimension’. In fact, such usage of the term may be also found in an overlap with that of multiplex networks [4, 5]. Thus, in order to avoid ambiguities, we call this kind of dimension as *connection dimension*. As a consequence, it derives directly from our chosen nomenclature that every connection dimension belongs to a node dimension.

In this way, our approach ensures that in any case one employs multidimensional networks, it can either mean networks with more than one node dimension, e.g., a dynamic network, or networks with more than one connection dimension (even if there is only one extra node dimension containing these connection dimensions), e.g., a social network with only two types of interactions, like family and professional. Thus, unlike for example in [4, 5], in which multidimensional networks refers basically to multiplex networks, we adopt the convention of defining a *general multidimensional network* as a network that has more than one node dimension and more than one connection dimension. As a consequence, both multilayer networks and dynamic networks become particular cases of general multidimensional networks. Also note that a network with only one node dimension and connection

⁸See first paragraph of this section for more examples of these individual features.

dimension is a monoplex (i.e., single-layer or monolayer) network [12, 15, 18] and, consequentially, is totally equivalent to a traditional graph.

In addition, we define a *high-order network* as a network that can be mathematically represented by a *high-order* MAG, i.e., a MAG with two or more aspects, each containing two or more elements [1, 29, 32]. Therefore, every node-aligned general multidimensional network is a high-order network. In fact, it is shown in section 3.3 in [31] that one can, for instance, construct a main-component graph $m(\mathcal{G})$, which is defined as the MAG \mathcal{G} with the unconnected composite vertices excluded. In this sense, if one allows the a priori exclusion of arbitrary composite vertices, it is possible to define MAGs that are not node-aligned, which would establish a complete equivalence between general multidimensional networks and high-order networks according to our nomenclature. However, in consonance with Section 2.1 and [1], we choose to stick with the notion of a MAG defined on a full set of possible composite vertices in this article. Hereafter, unless specified differently, multidimensional networks refers to node-aligned general multidimensional (i.e., high-order) networks and dimension refers to a node dimension. Whereas we are focusing on the multiplex case in this section, we will return to higher-order network properties in Section 5.

As in [12, 18], and similarly in [15], a *multiplex network* \mathcal{M} is a particular case of multilayer networks $M = (V_M, E_M, V, \mathbf{L})$ that are diagonally coupled, categorical, and potentially layer-connected, where $\mathbf{L} = \{L_\alpha\}_{\alpha=1}^1 = \{L_1\}$ and $|L_1| \geq 2$. From [18], we have that: a network M is *diagonally coupled* if and only if, for every interlayer edge $((u, \alpha), (v, \beta)) \in E_M$, where $\alpha \neq \beta$, one has that $u = v$; a network M is *categorically coupled* if and only if, for every $(u, \alpha), (u, \beta) \in V_M$, one has that $((u, \alpha), (u, \beta)) \in E_M$. Also in consonance with [18], we define here a condition for multiplex networks in order to ensure that the categorical couplings always apply to each pair of layers for at least one vertex $u \in V$: a network M is *potentially layer-connected* if and only if one has that $V_\alpha \cap V_\beta \neq \emptyset$, where $V_\gamma := \{v \mid (v, \gamma) \in V_M\}$ and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in L_1$ are arbitrary. This property is particularly important if M is not node-aligned. In general, most multiplex networks are considered to be node-aligned [18]. In fact, for example in [5, 26], multiplex networks are defined already assuming a node-alignment hypothesis. Moreover, as we already saw for node-aligned multilayer networks, we will have that any node-aligned multiplex network \mathcal{M} is equivalent to a particular type of second order MAG. Hereafter, unless specified differently, we will consider only node-aligned multiplex networks.

Let $G_{\mathcal{M}}$ be the second order simple MAG that is equivalent to an undirected node-aligned multiplex network \mathcal{M} . As in Section 4.1, note that diagonal coupling and categorical coupling are fixed and the presence of such composite edges are always recursively decidable from the composite vertices' labels.⁹ Let $G'_{\mathcal{M}} = (V, \mathcal{E}, L_1)$ denote the second order simple MAG $G_{\mathcal{M}}$ with all the interlayer edges excluded. In addition, $G'_{\mathcal{M}}$ belongs to a *recursively labeled* infinite family $F_{G'_{\mathcal{M}}}$ of arbitrary simple second order MAGs. Then, analogously to Section 4.1, the algorithmic information of $G_{\mathcal{M}}$ and the algorithmic information of $G'_{\mathcal{M}}$ can only differ by a constant (that only depends on the chosen language $\mathbf{L}_{\mathbf{U}}$) and, thus, will be negligible in our forthcoming results. With these definitions and nomenclature clarified in this section, as the reader may notice, $G'_{\mathcal{M}}$ is in fact an equivalent representation of a spatial simple TVG, except for a change in notation and nomenclature.

⁹See the construction of program s_1 in the proof of Theorem 4.1.

Therefore, we can now directly translate Theorem 4.1 and all the other results from Section 4.1:

Corollary 4.1. *Let $G'_{\mathcal{M}} = (V, \mathcal{E}, L_1)$ belong to a recursively labeled infinite family $F_{G'_{\mathcal{M}}}$ of simple second order MAGs. Then, there is a binary string $y \in \{0, 1\}^*$ that is an algorithmically characteristic string of $G'_{\mathcal{M}}$ such that*

$$K(y) \leq l(y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq |L_1(G'_{\mathcal{M}})| \left(\frac{|V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|^2 - |V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|}{2} \right) + \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})| |L_1(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|)) ,$$

$$K(x) \leq K(y) + \mathbf{O}(1) ,$$

$$K(x | y^*) \leq K(x | y) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \mathbf{O}(1) ,$$

$$K(y) \leq K(x) + \mathbf{O}(1) ,$$

and

$$K(y | x^*) \leq K(y | x) + \mathbf{O}(1) \leq \mathbf{O}(1)$$

hold, where x is the characteristic string of $G'_{\mathcal{M}}$.

Therefore, for large enough sets L_1 , $\mathbf{O}(1)$ -K-random undirected node-aligned multilayer networks with $\mathbf{L} = \{L_1\}$ (i.e., simple second order MAGs) carry at least

$$\left(\frac{(|V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})| |L_1(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|)^2 - |V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})| |L_1(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|}{2} \right) - |L_1(G'_{\mathcal{M}})| \left(\frac{|V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|^2 - |V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|}{2} \right) - \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|V(G'_{\mathcal{M}})| |L_1(G'_{\mathcal{M}})|))$$

more topological (or network) irreducible information than any node-aligned undirected multiplex network could carry. Moreover, it will also be a consequence of Theorem 5.1 that incompressible node-aligned general multilayer networks cannot be diagonally coupled and, therefore, cannot be multiplex networks. To this end, just replace an aspect corresponding to a set of layers with the first aspect (which is the set of vertices) and vice-versa. Thus, this section shows a comparison between the algorithmic complexity of multiplex network with a more general multilayer network. As in [28], another interesting line of research would be to compare the multiplex case with that of the network that, in turn, results from a restriction, or collapsing, of the multiplex topology: the aggregated graph (or aggregated multiplex network).

5. MULTIDIMENSIONAL DEGREE, CONNECTIVITY, DIAMETER, AND NON-SEQUENTIAL INTERDIMENSIONAL EDGES

We saw in Section 4.1 that snapshot-dynamic networks inevitably can carry only a number of bits of irreducible information upper bounded by $\mathbf{O}\left(|T| \left(\frac{|V|^2 - |V|}{2}\right)\right)$. In Section 4.2, we showed that the same also occurs for multiplex networks. Thus, one can define a non-empty class of (undirected) networks whose topological information characterizes a snapshot-like structure, in particular containing snapshot-dynamic networks or multiplex networks:

Definition 5.1. Let \mathcal{G}'_c be a simple second order MAG that belongs to a recursively labeled infinite family $F_{\mathcal{G}'_c}$ of simple second order MAGs. We say that the network mathematically represented by the MAG \mathcal{G}'_c is a (undirected) *snapshot-like multidimensional network* with respect to dimension (i.e., aspect) $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[i]$ if and only if there is an algorithmically characteristic string $y = \langle y', w \rangle \in \{0, 1\}^*$ of

\mathcal{G}'_c such that $w \in \{\emptyset\} \cup \{0, 1\}^*$ is independent of the choice of $\mathcal{G}'_c \in F_{\mathcal{G}'_c}$ and $y' = \langle x_1, \dots, x_{|\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[i]|} \rangle \in \{0, 1\}^*$, where $x_\alpha = \langle z_1, \dots, z_{k_j} \rangle \in \{0, 1\}^*$, $1 \leq \alpha \leq |\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[i]|$, $k_j = \binom{|\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G})[j]|}{2}$, $j \neq i$, $z_h \in \{0, 1\}$, $1 \leq h \leq k_j$, and, for every h -th element e' of $\{e|(u, \alpha, v, \alpha) \in \mathbb{E}_c(\mathcal{G}'_c)\}$, we have

$$z_h = 1 \iff e' \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}'_c) .$$

In other words, a (undirected) snapshot-like multidimensional network is a network that can be totally represented by a second order simple MAG whose composite edge set can be algorithmically determined by only informing a sequence of presences or absences of composite edges connecting two nodes within the same node dimension. Note that the proof of Theorem 4.1 and Corollary 4.1 guarantees that Definition 5.1 is satisfiable, for example, by snapshot-dynamic networks or multiplex networks that are node-aligned. The reader is also invited to note that Definition 5.1 can be generalized for simple MAGs with more than two aspects.

As we will show in this section, although an incompressible multidimensional network carries much more information in its topology than any snapshot-like multidimensional network—see Sections 4.1 and 4.2—, it displays some properties that may not be seen in real-world multidimensional networks, e.g., in those that can be univocally represented by snapshot-like multidimensional networks.

First, since a TVG is just a second order MAG, it is immediate to show in Corollary 5.1 that the previously studied Corollary 3.3, which holds for arbitrary order p [1], also applies to simple TVGs. Thus, for the sake of exemplification, we start with the dynamic case. Then, we generalize to the multidimensional case.

Corollary 5.1. *Let F_{G_t} be a recursively labeled infinite family F_{G_t} of simple TVGs G_t that are $\mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(G_t)|))$ - C -random. Then, the following hold for large enough $G_t \in F_{G_t}$, where $\mathbb{V}(G_t) = \mathbb{V}(G_t) \times \mathbb{T}(G_t)$:*

- (1) *The degree $\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{v})$ of a composite vertex $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(G_t)$ in a MAG $G_t \in F_{G_t}$ satisfies*

$$\left| \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{v}) - \left(\frac{|\mathbb{V}(G_t)| - 1}{2} \right) \right| = \mathbf{O} \left(\sqrt{|\mathbb{V}(G_t)|} \left(\mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(G_t)|)) \right) \right) .$$

- (2) *G_t has*

$$\frac{|\mathbb{V}(G_t)|}{4} \pm \mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(G_t)|)$$

disjoint paths of length 2 between each pair of composite vertices $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{V}(G_t)$.

- (3) *G_t has (composite) diameter 2.*

From Lemma 3.3, it is also immediate that there is an incompressible TVG that satisfies the conditions of Corollary 3.3 for some $\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$. In fact, this follows from Theorem 3.2 by assuming a family of initial segments of a K -random (i.e., prefix algorithmically random) real number. For example, one may take initial segments of the *halting probability* (or Chaitin's constant) [1]. Thus, from Lemma 3.3, Corollary 3.2, and Theorem 3.2, we have that Corollary 5.1 is satisfiable with $\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) = \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(G_t)|))$.

Now, let a *trans-temporal* edge be a composite edge $e = (u, t_i, v, t_j) \in \mathcal{E}(G_t)$ with $j \neq i \pm 1$ and $j \neq i$. Thus, the short composite diameter and high k -connectivity of

a $\mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathbf{G}_t)|))$ -C-random simple TVG ensures the existence of transtemporal edges in \mathbf{G}_t :

Corollary 5.2. *Let \mathbf{G}_t be a simple TVG satisfying Corollary 5.1 with $|\mathbb{T}(\mathbf{G}_t)| > 8$. Then, between every pair of vertices $u, v \in \mathbb{V}(\mathbf{G}_t)$ and time instants $t_i, t_j \in \mathbb{T}(\mathbf{G}_t)$ with $j > i + 2$, there is at least one transtemporal edge $e \in \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{G}_t)$.*

In fact, Corollary 5.2 holds as a particular case of undirected high-order networks (i.e., undirected node-aligned general multidimensional networks), as we will demonstrate below. The multilayered case with just one additional aspect besides the set of vertices is totally analogous to Corollary 5.2. For the multidimensional case, we will have that the first aspect still is the set of vertices. The second aspect in turn may be the set $\mathbb{T}(\mathcal{G}_c) = \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[2]$ of time instants or it may be the first layer type $\mathbb{L}_1(\mathcal{G}_c) = \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[2]$. The further aspects are any other layer type $\mathbb{L}_k(\mathcal{G}_c) = \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k + 1]$, where $k \leq |\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)| - 1$, or any other node dimension. Note that, unlike in [18], we refer to each element of $\mathbb{L}_k(\mathcal{G}_c)$ as a *layer* and to each $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k) \in \mathbb{L}_1(\mathcal{G}_c) \times \dots \times \mathbb{L}_k(\mathcal{G}_c)$ as a *layer tuple* (or composite layer), instead of, respectively, a elementary layer and a layer. Moreover, we refer to each set $\mathbb{L}_k(\mathcal{G}_c)$ as a *layer type* and to each arbitrary set $\mathbb{L}_i(\mathcal{G}_c) \times \dots \times \mathbb{L}_j(\mathcal{G}_c)$ as a *multilayer type*.

By generalizing the temporal case, let a *crosslayer* edge be a composite edge $e = (u, \dots, x_{ki}, \dots, x_{ps}, v, \dots, x_{kj}, \dots, x_{ps'}) \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ with $j \neq i \pm 1$ and $j \neq i$. In fact, in accordance with Section 4.2, both transtemporal and crosslayer edges are particular cases of what we call by a *non-sequential interdimensional edge*, should the aspect $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k]$ corresponds to an arbitrary node dimension of the general multidimensional network (instead of time or layers). This way, by noting that Corollary 3.3 applies to simple MAGs with order $p \geq 2$, as proved in [1], Corollary 5.2 becomes indeed a particular case of:

Theorem 5.1. *Let \mathcal{G}_c be any large enough $\mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|))$ -C-random simple MAG with order $p \geq 2$ that satisfies Corollary 3.3 with $\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) = \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|))$ such that*

$$|\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k]| = \frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \times \prod_{2 \leq h \leq p, h \neq k \leq p} |\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[h]|} > 8 ,$$

where $2 \leq k \leq p$. Then, between every pair of composite vertices

$$(u, \dots, x_{ki}, \dots, x_{ps})$$

and

$$(v, \dots, x_{kj}, \dots, x_{ps'})$$

in $\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ with $j > i + 2$, there is: at least one crosslayer edge $e \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$, if $\mathbb{L}_{k-1}(\mathcal{G}_c) = \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k]$; at least one transtemporal edge $e \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$, if $\mathbb{T}(\mathcal{G}_c) = \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k]$; or at least one non-sequential interdimensional edge $e \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$, if $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k]$ corresponds to any arbitrary node dimension.

Proof. Both transtemporal edges and crosslayer edges are particular cases of non-sequential interdimensional edges, except for a network interpretation of the aspect $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k]$. Thus, we will prove only the general case. First, if

$$(u, \dots, x_{ki}, \dots, x_{ps}, v, \dots, x_{kj}, \dots, x_{ps'}) \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c) ,$$

then it immediately satisfies the definition of non-sequential interdimensional edge. Since \mathcal{G}_c is large enough, satisfying Corollary 3.3 with

$$\delta(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) = \mathbf{O}(\log_2(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)) \leq \mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) ,$$

then the composite diameter becomes 2. Therefore, it only remains to investigate the case in which there is $(v', \dots, x_{kz}, \dots, x_{ps''}) \in \mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ with $x_{kz} \in \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[k]$ such that

$$(u, \dots, x_{ki}, \dots, x_{ps}, v', \dots, x_{kz}, \dots, x_{ps''}) \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$$

and

$$(v', \dots, x_{kz}, \dots, x_{ps''}, v, \dots, x_{kj}, \dots, x_{ps'}) \in \mathcal{E}(\mathcal{G}_c)$$

From Corollary 3.3, we have that, for every pair of composite vertices $(u, \dots, x_{ki}, \dots, x_{ps})$ and $(v, \dots, x_{kj}, \dots, x_{ps'})$, there are $\frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{4} \pm \mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)$ disjoint paths of length 2 between $(u, \dots, x_{ki}, \dots, x_{ps})$ and $(v, \dots, x_{kj}, \dots, x_{ps'})$. But, since \mathcal{G}_c can have arbitrarily large sets $\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)$ and

$$\frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \times \prod_{2 \leq h \leq p, h \neq k \leq p} |\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[h]|} > 8,$$

then the number of possible distinct composite vertices $(v', \dots, x_{kz}, \dots, x_{ps''})$ with $z = i$ or $z = j$ will be always smaller than or equal to

$$\begin{aligned} & 2 \left(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \times \prod_{2 \leq h \leq p, h \neq k \leq p} |\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[h]| \right) = \\ & = 2 |\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \left(\frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \times \prod_{2 \leq h \leq p, h \neq k \leq p} |\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{G}_c)[h]|} \right)^{-1} < \\ & < 2 \frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{8} = \lim_{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \rightarrow \infty} 2 |\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \left(\frac{1}{8} - \frac{\mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|)}{2 |\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|} \right) = \\ & = \lim_{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|}{4} - \mathbf{o}(|\mathbb{V}(\mathcal{G}_c)|) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in the limit, it will eventually be strictly smaller than the number of distinct composite vertices connecting $(u, \dots, x_{ki}, \dots, x_{ps})$ and $(v, \dots, x_{kj}, \dots, x_{ps'})$. Therefore, there will be at least one composite vertex $(v', \dots, x_{kz}, \dots, x_{ps''})$ with $i+1 < z$, $z+1 < j$, $z < i$, or $j < z$. \square

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have extended the results from [38] and [1] and studied the plain and prefix algorithmic randomness of high-order networks that can be formally represented by multispect graphs (MAGs). We have dealt with the incompressibility of multidimensional networks, especially node-aligned undirected multilayer networks or dynamic networks. First, we have compared time-varying graphs with other snapshot-like representations of dynamic networks. We have shown that incompressible snapshot-dynamic networks carry an amount of topological algorithmic information that is linearly dominated by the size of the set of time instants. To this end, we have applied a study of a worst-case lossless compression of the algorithmically characteristic string of the network. The algorithmically characteristic string contains all the necessary information to computationally represent the entire network such that it is potentially agnostic with respect to node labeling or indexing.

Then, after a careful analysis of previous nomenclature and assumptions in the literature, we have shown that the same results can be applied to multiplex networks, where the set of layers plays the role of the set of time instants instead.

In this regard, we have shown that both snapshot-dynamic networks and multiplex networks are two particular and distinct cases of snapshot-like multidimensional networks, but that are equivalent (except by a constant that only depends on the chosen universal programming language) in terms of algorithmic complexity.

In addition, from previous results, we have shown that the topological information carried by incompressible general multidimensional networks is on the quadratic order of the size of the set of time instants instead. Therefore, the maximum amount of topological information of an incompressible snapshot-like multidimensional network may be much smaller than the amount of topological information of an incompressible general multidimensional network.

Secondly, we have investigated some topological properties of incompressible multidimensional networks. To this end, we have applied previous results for incompressible MAGs. We have shown that these networks have very short diameter, high k -connectivity, and degrees on the order of half of the network size within a strong-asymptotically dominated standard deviation. Therefore, these theoretical findings relate lossless compression of multidimensional networks with their network topological properties. For example, these properties are expected to happen in both artificial or real-world high-order networks that carry a maximal and irreducible network topology in terms of information content. In this way, such theoretical results may give rise to future tools that could be applied to, for instance, high-order network summarization algorithms and the reducibility problem (i.e., the problem of finding the aggregate graph that represents the original multidimensional network and preserves its core properties during network analysis).

Furthermore, we have also shown the presence of transtemporal or crosslayer edges (i.e., edges linking vertices at non-sequential time instants or layers) in those incompressible multidimensional networks. Although representations of more general forms of multidimensional networks may carry much more topological information, this presence of transtemporal or crosslayer edges may not correspond to some underlying structures of real-world networks. Specifically, this is the case of snapshot-dynamic networks, where transtemporal edges would not have any physical correspondence to connections that ‘jump across time instants’. On the other hand, in the crosslayer case, it can make sense for some multilayer networks, where the indexing or ordering of the layers does not correspond to any pre-established physical structure. Thus, with the purpose of bringing algorithmic randomness to the context of multidimensional networks—or, in general, complex networks—, our theoretical results suggest that estimating or analyzing both the incompressibility and the network topological properties of real-world networks cannot be taken into a universal approach. Similarly to what we have shown for snapshot-based representations of multidimensional networks, the algorithmic randomness of certain networks may be strongly dependent on the underlying constraints or structure of the network.

This study and approach is key to move forward from statistical approaches to non-statistical challenges in the context of network science and beyond, such as those related to model generation, feature selection and data dimensionality reduction as already started in [36]. For example, in dynamic multilayer networks,

one important challenge is to disentangle the cause and effect between and inside different networks over time, a problem relevant to almost every area of science where processes can be represented as networks and interactions as connections to other networks.

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